

Determinants of Bankruptcy Prediction and Implication on Stock Prices in Oil and Gas Mining Sectors in Indonesia Stock Exchange Period 2012-2016

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Abstract:

This study aims to examine and analyze the influence of bankruptcy prediction model and implication to the stock price of oil and gas companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Research data is the annual data for the 2012-2016 observation period obtained from the companies' annual report. The sampling method used was purposive sampling. From a population of 9 companies, 8 companies met the criteria to be the sample. Simple regression analysis results showed that the value of the Z-Score affect the stock price. The result of the simultaneous multiple regression analysis on financial ratios of the Z-Score affects the stock prices, partially showed the ratio of WC/TA negatively affect the stock price and ratio RE/TA and EBIT/TA negatively affect the stock price; ratio MVE/BVD have a positive effect on stock prices..

Keywords: Altman Z-Score, WC/TA, RE/TA, EBIT/TA, MVE/BVD, the stock price

Introduction

Public company performance can be reflected in stock price movements in the capital market. Companies that do not pay attention to the performance of the company can experience financial distress and potentially experience bankruptcy. This condition makes investors and creditors worry about investing their money in the capital market (Endri, 2018). Oil and gas companies have capital-intensive characteristics and to fulfill the funding, a number of oil and gas companies issue shares on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

The trend of stock prices of the oil and gas sub-sector experienced fluctuations, namely in 2013 and 2014 which increased by 23% and 43% from the previous year, then in 2015 and 2016, the average share price decreased by 49% and 15% respectively. The fluctuations in stock prices and the decline in world oil prices, increase the risk of bankruptcy and require investors to be more careful in buying the stock of oil and gas companies.

The risk of corporate bankruptcy can be measured by analyzing Altman's financial ratios from financial statements (Altman, 1968). Research on the effect of bankruptcy predictions using Altman Z-Score and its financial ratios on stock prices has been done by many previous researchers. However, these studies show different results so that further research is needed to prove the predictive influence of Altman Z-Score and its financial ratios have implications for the share price of the oil and gas mining sub-sector (Syamni, 2018).

Literature Review

Stock

Stocks can be defined as proof of the participation of capital ownership in a company. The market price of a stock can influence an investor's decision to invest in the issuer's company. Stock prices can also be one indicator of the success of company management (Benyamin and Endri, 2019).

Pricing Model

Pricing Model is a model used to predict expected stock income. Models that are widely used such as the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) and multifactor.

Financial Distress

Financial distress is financial difficulties or liquidity as the beginning of bankruptcy due to a decline in financial conditions. According to Altman, financial distress can be caused by economic failure and financial failure. In normal conditions, financial distress is mostly due to management weaknesses.

Altman Z-Score Prediction

. Altman Z-Score analysis is a method to predict the health condition of a company by using 4 financial ratios (Altman, 1968, 2000). The following is the formula used for non-manufacturing companies in developing countries.

$$Z' = 6,56 X1 + 3,26 X2 + 6,72 X3 + 1,05 X4$$

X1 = Working Capital / Total Assets

X2 = Retained Earnings / Total Assets

X3 = Earnings Before Interest and Taxes / Total Assets

X4 = Market Value Equity / Book Value Debt

The criteria used to predict the bankruptcy of a company are as follows:

- | | |
|-----------------------|--|
| Z Score > 2.60 | Safe zone (healthy company) |
| 1.10 < Z-Score < 2.60 | Grey Area (between bankrupt and not bankrupt). |
| Z score < 1.10 | Bankrupt Zone |

The financial ratios used are:

- **Working Capital to Total Assets (WC/TA)** is the financial ratio used to measure a company's liquidity
- **Retained Earnings to Total Assets (RE/TA)** is a financial ratio used to measure a company's ability to generate profits during the company's operating period
- **Earnings Before Interest and Taxes to Total Assets (EBIT/TA)** is the financial ratio used to measure the return on assets. It can also measure how much the productivity of borrowed funds is productive.
- **Market Value of Equity to Book Value of Total Debt (MVE/BVD)** is used to measure a company's ability to meet its long-term obligations from its own capital.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Framework Research Model

Based on the above framework, the proposed hypothesis is as follows:

- H1: Z-Score has a positive effect on stock prices

- H2: Working Capital to Total Assets (WC / TA) has a positive effect on stock prices
- H3: Retained Earnings to Total Assets has a positive effect on stock prices
- H4: Earnings Before Interest and Taxes to Total Assets (EBIT/TA) has a positive effect on stock prices
- H5: Ratio of Capital Market Value / Book Value Total Debt (X4) has a positive effect on stock prices

Methodology

Population and Sampling Techniques

The population used is public companies in the oil and gas sub-sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2012 - 2016. The method used is purposive sampling method with the following criteria:

- Public companies in the oil and gas sub-sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the period 2012-2016.
- The company has published complete financial statements from 2012 - 2016.

There are 9 public oil and gas companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2013 - 2017, as many as 8 companies were selected as research samples.

Table 1. Research Sample

Code	Company Name	Code	Company Name
APEX	Apexindo Pratama Duta Tbk.	MEDC	Medco Energi Internasional Tbk.
BIPI	Benakat Petroleum Energy Tbk.	RUIS	Radiant Utama Interinsco Tbk.
ELSA	Elnusa Tbk.	ARTI	Ratu Prabu Energi Tbk.
ENRG	Energi Mega Persada Tbk.	ESSA	Surya Esa Perkasa Tbk

Data Analysis Method

The research data were analyzed using Data Panel Regression analysis by using E-Views version 10 to find out the influence of Z-Score and its financial ratios on stock prices.

Operational Variables

The operational variables used in this study are as follows::

Table 2. Operational Variables

No.	Variables	Indicator	Scale	Reference
1	Price (Y)	<i>Price Closing Stck</i>	Ratio	Annual Report
2	Z-Score	$Z' = 6,56 X1 + 3,26 X2 + 6,72 X3 + 1,05 X4$	Ratio	Annual Report
3	WC to TA (X1)	$\frac{Working\ Capital}{Total\ Asset}$	Ratio	Annual Report
4	RE to TA (X2)	$\frac{Retained\ Earning}{Total\ Asset}$	Ratio	Annual Report
5	EBIT to TA (X3)	$\frac{EBIT}{Total\ Asset}$	Ratio	Annual Report
6	MVE to BVD (X4)	$\frac{Market\ Value\ of\ Equity}{Booked\ Value\ of\ Total\ Debt}$	Ratio	Annual Report

Result

Effect of Altman Z-Score Prediction on Stock Prices

Descriptive Statistics Analysis

The descriptive statistics of the research variables can be seen in the following table:

Table 3. Statistics-Descriptive

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.Dev
Price (Y)	40	50	3800	986.95	1176.294
Z-Score (Z)	40	- 6,65	15,24	2,142	4,05

Based on the table above shows that the lowest value of Z-Score is equal to -6.65, which means there are companies that are predicted to go bankrupt.

Regression Models Selection

Choosing the proper model for research is critical and essential to avoid the bias from the regression results, ensure the consistency and achieve reliable results for the study. The proper model can be determined through the Chow test, Hausman test and Lagrange Multiplier test on the common effect model, fixed effect model and random effect model with the following results: :

Table 4. Methodology Test

Test	p-value ($\alpha=10\%$)	Result
Chow	0,0000	Fixed Effect
Hausman	0,3992	Random Effect
Lagrange Multiplier	0,0000	Random Effect

Based on the Hausman and Lagrangre Multiplier test, the most appropriate model is the Random Effect Model with the panel data regression equation as follows:

$$Y = 869,12 + 55 Z$$

Hypothesis Test Result.

The calculation results using the Random Effect Model panel data regression equation in this study as follows:

Table 5. Hypotesis Test Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	869.1241	391.6151	2.219333	0.0325
Z	55.00098	27.51874	1.998674	0.0528
R-squared	0.095784			
Adjusted R-squared	0.071989			
F-statistic	4.025349			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.051977			

Based on the T-Test and F-Test ($\alpha = 10\%$) the variable Z-Score has a significant effect on stock prices. The results of Goodness of fit R-squared 0.095784 indicate that 9.58%, the independent variable can explain the ups and downs of stock prices and 90.42%, influenced by other factors outside the research.

Effect of Altman Z-Score Financial Ratios on Stock Prices

Descriptive Statistics Analysis

The descriptive statistics of the research variables can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. Statistics-Descriptive

	WC/TA(X1)	RE/TA(X2)	EBIT/TA(X3)	MVE/BVD(X4)	Stock Price (Y)
Mean	0.019250	0.083750	0.026000	1.489750	986.95
Median	0.055000	0.125000	0.040000	0.305000	241.5
Maximum	0.440000	0.410000	0.150000	12.08000	3800
Minimum	-0.380000	-0.780000	-0.380000	0.090000	50
Std. Dev.	0.189917	0.209831	0.093419	2.704869	1176.29
Skewness	-0.259818	-1.810497	-2.469566	2.573891	1.02
Kurtosis	2.509268	8.407821	10.91750	8.941556	2.57
Jarque-Bera	0.851399	70.59355	145.1363	103.0029	7.260199
Probability	0.653313	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.026514
Observations	40	40	40	40	40

Regression Models Selection

Choosing the proper model for research is critical and essential to avoid the bias from the regression results, ensure the consistency and achieve reliable results for the study. The proper model can be determined through the Chow test, Hausman test and Lagrange Multiplier test on the common effect model, fixed effect model and random effect model with the following results: :

Table 7. Methodology Test

Test	p-value ($\alpha=10\%$)	Result
Chow	0,0000	<i>Fixed Effect</i>
Hausman	0,0862	<i>Fixed Effect</i>
Lagrange Multiplier	0,0000	<i>Random Effect</i>

Based on the Hausman and Lagrangre Multiplier test, the most appropriate model is the Random Effect Model with the panel data regression equation as follows:

$$Y = 788,6123 - 1023,173 X1 + 610,6983 X2 + 181,2039 X3 + 108,9994 X4$$

Hypothesis Test Result.

The panel data regression results using the Fixed Effect Model in this study as follows:

Table 8. Result of Fixed Effect Model in Financial Ratio Altman Z-Score

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	788.6123	124.9367	6.312094	0.0000
X1	-1023.173	589.5862	-1.735409	0.0937
X2	610.6983	1465.291	0.416776	0.6800
X3	181.2039	2193.759	0.082600	0.9348
X4	108.9994	40.98056	2.659783	0.0128
R-squared	0.873241			
Adjusted R-squared	0.823443			
F-statistic	17.53563			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

F-Test

With a probability level of 90% ($\alpha = 10\%$), the value of Prob (F-Statistic) = 0.0000 < 0.1, means the independent variables WC / TA (X1), RE / TA (X2), EBIT / TA (X3) and MVE / BVD (X4) together have a significant effect on the dependent variable of Stock Price

T-Test

Based on table 7 above, it's been found that H0 (X1) rejected, H0 (X2) accepted, H0 (X3) accepted and H0 (X4) rejected, so it is concluded as follows:

Table 9. T-Test Results

Variable	Effect	Significant
WC/TA	Negative	Significant
RE/TA	Positive	Not Significant
EBIT/TA	Positive	Not Significant
MVE/BVD	Positive	Significant

Goodness of Fit

The results of Goodness of fit R-squared 0.873241 show that 87.32%, the independent variable can influence stock price movements and 12.68%, influenced by other factors outside this study

Discussion

The Effect of Altman Z-Score on Stock Prices

Z-Score has a significant and positive effect on stock prices. This result is in line with the hypothesis in this study where Z-Score has a positive and significant effect on stock prices. These results indicate that Z-Score is important information for investors. The relationship with a positive sign indicates that the higher the Z-Score, the higher the stock price and vice versa. This means that the higher the Z-Score of a company, the smaller the potential for bankruptcy of the company. This research is in line with previous research from Roykhan (2012), Apergis, *et al.*, (2011) and Karaca *et al.*, (2017).

Effect of Working Capital to Total Assets (WC / TA) on Stock Prices

Working capital to total assets (WC / TA) has a negative and significant effect on stock prices. The negative effect on WC / TA is not in line with the hypothesis in this study. This can be interpreted that increasing WC / TA means that the company has not utilized assets efficiently so that it can reduce stock profits. This research is in line with previous research from Siregar (2008), and Foo and Pathak (2016).

Effect of Retained Earnings to Total Assets (RE/TA) on Stock Prices

Retained earnings to total assets (RE / TA) have a positive and not significant effect on stock prices. This result is not in line with the hypothesis in this study where RE / TA has a positive and significant effect on stock prices. Retained earnings are profitability ratios that show the company's ability to generate profits during the company's operating period. The longer the company operates, the more likely it is to increase the accumulated retained earnings. However, this cannot guarantee that the company is able to survive in a crisis so that investors are suspected of not considering the length of time the company was established, Ardian *et al.*, (2014).

On the other hand, retained earnings show how much corporate income is not paid in the form of dividends to its shareholders. Dividends have an important meaning for investors because they show that management has worked hard to achieve maximum profit growth. However, not only companies that increase their net income to pay dividends, there are issuers that have a lower net income but still pay dividends. Therefore, investors that are investing in shares do not pay attention to RE / TA.

Effect of Earnings Before Interest and Taxes to Total Assets (EBIT/TA) on Stock Prices

EBIT / total asset ratio (EBIT / TA) has a positive and not significant effect on stock prices. This result is not in line with the hypothesis that EBIT / TA has a positive and significant effect on stock prices. This shows that investors are more likely to see the net profit of a company because when the EBIT is high, it doesn't always necessarily make the company's net profit high, as it is still very dependent on the size of the interest rate and tax to be paid. The results of this study are supported by Ananda's research (2018), but are not in line with the research of Sukmawati *et al.*, (2014) and Lestari *et al.*, (2016)

Effect of Market Value of Equity to Book Value of Total Debt (MVE/BVD) on Stock Prices

Market Value of Equity to Book Value of Total Debt (MVE / BVD) has a positive and significant effect on stock prices. So that the higher the MVE / BVD of a company, the higher the company's stock price, too. This means that the higher the MVE / BVD company shows the ability of the company to fulfill long-term obligations from the value of its own capital. The greater the MVE / BVD ratio, the lesser the risk and the healthier the company's financial condition will be. This result is in line with the hypothesis that MVE / BVD has a positive effect on stock prices. The results of this study are also in line with previous studies from Almansour (2015) and Sukmawati *et al.*, (2014).

Conclusion

Based on the results of the previous research and discussion, some conclusions can be stated as follows:

1. Z-Score has a positive and significant effect on the stock prices of oil and gas in 2012-2016.
2. The WC / TA ratio has a negative and significant effect on the stock prices of oil and gas in 2012-2016.
3. The RE / TA ratio has a positive and insignificant effect on the stock prices of oil and gas in 2012-2016.
4. The EBIT / TA ratio has a positive and insignificant effect on the stock prices of oil and gas in 2012-2016.

5. The MVE / BVD ratio has a positive and significant effect on the stock prices of oil and gas in 2012-2016.

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